

Data Analytics Can Add Value in the Process Industry

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Abstract: While Nina Thornhill spent time at the University of Alberta, Canada, in 2000/2001 she interacted with Matrikon, working on plant-wide oscillations and controller performance assessment.

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My first interaction with Prof. Nina Thornhill was when she was a visiting faculty at the University of Alberta as part of the Industrial Research Chair program. The program was a three-way partnership between industry, technology provider and University and proved to be a catalyst for many ideas in what is now known as data analytics or advanced analytics area for process industry.

Working with Matrikon at the time, we were trying hard to prove to industry that controller and process monitoring technology could add value. One problem that came up time and again was the issue of diagnosing plant wide oscillations, which could be easily detected with the controller performance monitoring technology but were not easy to diagnose.

The challenge was integrating first principles process knowledge and raw data analysis in addressing this problem. Remember discussing this problem with Prof. Thornhill and Prof. Shah at the time at length. Prof. Thornhill's group did a lot of seminal work in this area, especially through the use of

transfer entropy methods and embedding causality information through automatic parsing of P&IDs. Much of this work was probably ahead of its time for the industry. With the current focus squarely on data analytics, industry will hopefully realize the value of this work and in turn motivate further research in this area.

I also had the pleasure of interacting with Prof. Thornhill as few years ago when my mentee at Saudi Aramco, Hamza Hamadah, ended up going to Imperial College as her Master's student. The research focus at her group remained distinctly industrial with his Master's topic covering dynamic optimization of industrial compression trains.

I will always recall the humility in her approach and clarity with which she approached a new problem.

All the best to Prof. Thornhill as she enters a new phase of her life. Industry in general has benefited significantly from her work and controller and process monitoring as an area has much to thank her for!